

ABOUT PSYCHOLINGUISTIC RESEARCHERS

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Abstract. *In recent years, new areas of linguistics have emerged and begun to develop called the anthropocentric paradigm, which studies the close connection between language and the human factor. One of these areas is psycholinguistics, which studies the points of contact between psychology and linguistics, the mental and emotional state of a person, and processes related to language.*

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In recent years, new directions of linguistics have appeared and started to develop under the name of the anthropocentric paradigm, studying the issues of the close connection between language and the human factor. One such field is psycholinguistics, which studies the points of convergence of psychology and linguistics, the mental and emotional state of a person, and the processes related to language.

George Miller, a famous American psychologist, one of the founders of cognitive psychology, and a scientist who made a great contribution to the creation of psycholinguistics, believes that psycholinguistics is one of the most complex fields, because linguists and psychologists are far from each other and do not understand each other. "Linguists and psychologists talk about different things... Grammarians are more interested in what people can say than what they actually say, which annoys psychologists, and psychologists insist on supplementing intuition with objective evidence, which annoys linguists", says J. Miller. Indeed, if linguists emphasize what language units should be used in what situation, psychologists analyze exactly what situations speech is created in relation to. The goal of psycholinguistics is to combine these two, to clarify the aspects of speech related to the situation, based on the rules of language.

According to linguist N. Purba, psycholinguistics includes three main points: language production, language perception and language acquisition. Language production (here, speech production) refers to processes related to the creation and expression of meaning through language. Language comprehension refers to the processes involved in interpreting and understanding written and spoken language. Language acquisition refers to the processes of acquiring a mother tongue or a second language.

P. Fress explained psycholinguistics as "the science of the relationship between our expressive and communicative needs and tools represented by language". Therefore, psycholinguistics is a direction that studies the process of choosing and using linguistic tools in the implementation of communicative and expressive tasks of language.

Two stages in the development of psycholinguistics are recognized by linguists, and the first stage lasted from the 1950s to the 1990s, when psycholinguistics was formed as a separate field and was freed from the chains of behaviorism. The second stage is the stage that is still ongoing.

The term "psycholinguistics" was first mentioned by the American scientist Jacob Robert Yankor in the book "An Objective Psychology of Grammar". Psycholinguistics, as an

interdisciplinary field that studies language phenomena from a psychological perspective, is defined by Cantor's student Nicholas Henry Pronko in his article *Language and Psycholinguistics: A Review*. Then this theory was developed by Charles E. Osgood and Thomas A. Sebeok. In 1951, the Social Science Research Council of Cornell University held the first conference dedicated to psycholinguistics. After this conference, the Committee on Linguistics and Psychology was formed and Charles E. Osgood was appointed as the head of this committee. After the conference, it is necessary to recognize that two important steps have been taken in the field of psycholinguistics. The first of them was a large seminar held at Indiana University in 1953, and the second was the publication of the book "Psycholinguistics: a survey of theory and research problems" based on the results of the seminar. The field of psycholinguistics was also influenced by the direction of generative linguistics founded by Noam Chomsky. Generative linguistics emphasizes internal knowledge, which means what people can do with language, how to acquire language and retain it in long-term memory. Through this, it was recognized that it is necessary to abandon the focus on the analysis and description of language units related to structural linguistics.

According to Sami Boudela, the influence of generative linguistics on psycholinguistics was the opposite of psychology. The author admits that at least two psychological paradigms existed in the emergence of psycholinguistics. The first of these was Information Theory, which emphasized probability and redundancy in language communication and viewed the language processor as a device that creates and understands sentences by moving from one state to another. The second research paradigm was the paradigm of behaviorism, which dominated until the end of the 50s of the 20th centuries. According to this paradigm, language was viewed as one of all the behaviors of a living organism, such as moving, thinking, and feeling. Behaviorists argue that such behavior can be learned and understood as a relationship between input (stimulus) and output (response). There is no need to invoke internal physiological phenomena or hypothetical structures such as consciousness. No distinction is made between concrete publicly observable processes, such as eating an apple or drinking a cup of payola tea, and abstract unobservable processes, such as thinking and feeling. So language is like any other behavior and its acquisition and use can be learned with the standard behaviorist toolkit using conditioning and reinforcement. Thus, language is viewed by information theorists as a device that exchanges information, creating sentences by passing from one state to another, and behaviorists as behavior. understood as an action.

In 1959, Noam Chomsky wrote a review of Skinner's book, which became more famous than the book itself. In this review, Chomsky states that behaviorism is incapable of studying natural language and proposes his theory of transformational or generative grammar. Transformational grammar incorporated the issues of language construction and human knowledge of language, and psycholinguistic experiments to test this theory contributed to the development of psycholinguistics.

Based on this, D. Carroll divides the formation and development of psycholinguistics into 4 periods:

- 1) European early psycholinguistics - the stage of creation of the first psychological laboratory by V. Wundt in 1879;
- 2) the phase of dominance of behaviorism and verbal behavior ideas in the USA since the 1920s;

3) psycholinguistics of the next period - work after the seminars of 1951-1953, Chomsky's research, the creation of transformative grammar, the stage when the "Chomsky revolution" was realized;

4) psycholinguistics of the present period - implementation of interdisciplinary research, this period covers the last 15-20 years.

According to linguists who have studied psycholinguistics, "psycholinguistics can be said to have emerged in the history of philosophy in connection with the observation of psychology." Scientist Katernya Diukar admits that the foundation stone of this direction was laid at the beginning of the 19th century. It is stated by the scientist that Wilhelm von Humboldt's desire to separate language and speech is aimed at determining the relationship of language to thinking. Recognizing that language and speech are indeed separate and closely related phenomena, noting that language and speech are related to human consciousness.

Wilhelm von Humboldt's scientific and theoretical views are presented in the form of antinomies specific to the nature of language, the first of these antinomies is the antinomy of language and thought. Language and thinking are interrelated and mutually demanding phenomena. The second antinomy is the antinomy of language and speech, and the scientist distinguished the specific aspects of language and speech. The third antinomy - the antinomy of speech and understanding refers to the opposites in the communication between the creator of the speech and its receiver - the recipient. Creating a speech is one aspect of the issue, understanding it and accepting it as the author wants is the second aspect. The fourth antinomy covers the objective and subjective aspects of speech, while the fifth antinomy refers to the collective and individual characteristics of language.

As mentioned above, the foundations of the psycholinguistic approach to language can be seen from Humboldt's views. It can be said that the interrelationship of language and thinking, the separation of language and speech, as well as the contradictions and dependencies in the creation and reception of speech determine the main directions of psycholinguistics. In particular, the issue of the author's psychological state, mood, and the receiver's psychological state during the creation of the speech is the basis for determining the psycholinguistic aspects of communication.

Wilhelm von Humboldt's student G. Steintal also approaches the phenomena of language and speech in a unique way and emphasizes psychological factors in the formation of speech. According to G. Steintal, language is an action, a process. The author distinguishes three main states in the act of speaking: organic-mechanical movement, psychic mechanics, reflection of thinking and logical thoughts. In this case, as an organic-mechanical movement, the physiological state of a person during speech delivery, the processes of speech organs are meant, and as psychic mechanics, the mental state of a person and the effect of psychological processes on speech are understood. Reflection of thinking and logical processes, when evaluated from the point of view of today's modern cognitive linguistics, means the verbalization of concepts in human thinking.

According to Onwuka Ngozi and Ohaka, psycholinguistics or the psychology of language studies the psychological and neurobiological factors that enable humans to acquire, process, understand and use language [Onwuka Ngozi, F., & Ohaka, C.K. A Psycholinguistic Approach to Language Teaching and Learning: Problems and Prospects. The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies. 2019.]. This means that the ideas of G. Steintal are also supported by modern linguists.

Willem Levelt notes that the history of psycholinguistics goes back to the end of the 18th century: Although most psycholinguists believe that the history of this field began with Chomsky's "cognitive revolution" in the late 1950s and 1960s, the history of empirical psycholinguistics actually goes back to the end of the 18th century. is worn. Psycholinguistics has four historical roots, which were united by the end of the 19th century. By this time, the science known as psycholinguistics or the psychology of language was created. The first of these roots is comparative-historical linguistics, which raised the issue of the psychological origin of language. The second root was the study of the brain and language, in which the findings of Franz Gall, Broca and Wernicke are noteworthy. The third root was the everyday approach to child development that emerged in Rousseau's Emily. The fourth root was an experimental laboratory approach to speech and language processing that arose out of Francis Donders' mental chronometry. Wilhelm Wundt combined these four approaches in his 1900 monumental *Die Sprache*. These four roots of psycholinguistics developed in very different contexts until the 20th century.

The history of the development of psycholinguistics is described in the article "On the historical development of psycholinguistics" by Joseph F. Kess. It contrasts Wundt's psycholinguistics with contemporary psycholinguistics of the past 50 years and charts our progress in current psycholinguistic research through the ages of formative, linguistic, and cognitive science. Particular attention is paid to models and metaphors based on natural language and computational representation of intelligence as an information processing device.

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According to D. Gabris-Barker, psycholinguistics originates from psychology and relies on other cognitive and practical sciences. Traditionally, the goal of psycholinguistic research is focused on the processes associated with acts of verbal communication between people: language comprehension, speech creation, and its acquisition. As the name suggests, psycholinguistics derives from psychology and draws on theoretical, cognitive, and applied linguistics as important sources, as well as cognitive science, biology, neuroscience, and anthropology... In other words, when we define psycholinguistics, we define it as Lum can be described as the psychology of language based on the interaction of psychological and neurobiological factors at the level of communication in people, understanding and production of verbal messages in the act of interaction. We recognize that psychology and linguistics are equally important in the origin of psycholinguistics.

Psycholinguistics exists and develops in close genetic connection with psychology. At the same time, psychology deals with interpersonal communication, one of its main tools is language. Just as there are different opinions about the origin of psycholinguistics, there are also different opinions and views about the issue of the research scope and scope of this direction.

John Field in his "Psycholinguistics. The key concepts" - "Psycholinguistics. In his book "Basic Concepts", he acknowledges that the field of psycholinguistics is broad in scope and mentions that the field deals with the following issues:

1. Language processes. Reading, writing, speaking, listening comprehension skills, language connection with memory.

2. Vocabulary and its use. Ability to memorize words and use them selectively when needed.

3. Learning the language. In this, the issue of the baby's acquisition of the mother tongue is taken into account.

4. Special circumstances. In these cases, the impact of physical disabilities (deafness, blindness), conditions related to brain damage (medical conditions such as dyslexia, aphasia) on language and speech is understood.

5. Mind and language relations. The issue of language taking place in the human mind, development, and the fact that language is a phenomenon unique to humans.

6. Issues of second language acquisition and its use.

A. Chaer admits that there are several directions of psycholinguistics:

1. Theoretical psycholinguistics. This direction studies the theoretical foundations of processes related to human consciousness and language.

2. Developmental psycholinguistics. This direction deals with language acquisition processes. This includes the processes of mastering the mother tongue, as well as the processes of mastering a second or foreign language. Phonological, semantic, and syntactic bases of the development of language acquisition processes are the study units of this direction.

3. Social psycholinguistics - social psycholinguistics covers the social nature and social aspects of language.

4. Educational psycholinguistics. Through this direction, the role of language in the development of reading, the issues of speech development to express thoughts and ideas are studied.

5. Neuro-psycholinguistics. This course explores the connections between language, speech production, and the human mind. In this, neuroscience experts studied the working mechanisms of the human mind in the creation of speech.

6. Experimental psycholinguistics - with the help of experimental psycholinguistics, psychological processes related to language and speech are studied on the basis of experiments.

7. Applied psycholinguistics - applied psycholinguistics deals with the issues of applying the practical results of the six psycholinguistic directions mentioned above. According to M. Shkhapatseva, the subject of psycholinguistics is very broad, and today its main focus is on the following main directions:

- speech understanding, memorization and production mechanisms;
- speech production and comprehension processes;
- language performance in speech production and perception;
- language use mechanisms;
- mental dictionary;
- language acquisition (local, foreign);
- ontogeny of children's speech, innate language mechanisms, child's linguistic environment;

- phenomenon of bilingualism;
- the mechanism of human speech, features of its formation and activity;
- language (speech) disorders;

- intellectual processes in communication.

Analyzing the definitions and views given to psycholinguistics, psycholinguistics is accepted and interpreted in several ways today:

1. Psycholinguistics is a branch of linguistics:

a) psycholinguistics as a type of linguistic research (L.V. Sakharniy, K.F. Sedov, I.N. Gorelov);

b) as a special direction of theoretical linguistics (A.Y. Suprun);

c) as an experimental direction of linguistics (G.D. Prideaux).

2. Psycholinguistics is a branch of psychology (A.A. Leontiev, D.W. Carrol).

3. Psycholinguistics is a related direction between the fields of linguistics and psychology.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to interpret psycholinguistics in the third sense - as a field that studies the interrelated aspects of psychology and linguistics.

Therefore, the scope of psycholinguistics is wide, and with the help of psycholinguistic experiences and knowledge, it becomes possible to research the theoretical aspects of language and create theories related to the nature of language.

REFERENCES

1. A.A.Leontev Basic psycholinguistics.M., – 1999.
2. A.Chaer. Psycholinguistics: Kajian Teori. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta. –2015.
3. D.Gabryś-Barker. Psycholinguistics for Foreign Language Teachers: A Diachronic Perspective. Anglica Wratislaviensia. – 2022. P.152.
4. John Field. Psycholinguistics: the key concepts. London; New York: Routledge.– 2004.
5. J.F.Kess. On the developing history of psycholinguistics. Language Sciences. – 1991. 13, 1-20.
6. D.Kateryna. Evolution of psycholinguistic theories in word-making processes//Scientific Journal of Polonia University. 46(2021).
7. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.23856/4602>.
8. L.Willem. A History of Psycholinguistics: The Pre-Chomskyan Era – Oxford, 2012; online edn, Oxford Academic, 24 Jan. 2013), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199653669.001.0001>, accessed 24 Nov. 2023.
9. M.Kh.Shkhatpseva.Communication v zerkale psiholingvistiki// <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kommunikatsiya-v-zerkale-psiholingvistiki>.
10. Purba Norita. The role of psycholinguistics in language learning and teaching. Tell Journal, Volume 6, Number 1, April. – 2018. P.47.
11. P. Fraisse La psycho-linguistique // Problems de psycho-linguistique. – Paris. – 1965. P.5.
12. W.D.Carroll Psychology of Language. Fifth edition. – 2008.
13. J.F. Kess. On the developing history of psycholinguistics. Language Sciences, 1991. 13, 1-20.
14. Karimova Nargiza Mamatkadirovna,. (2022). Pedagogical Conditions for the Development of Intercultural Communication Among Students. Czech Journal of Multidisciplinary Innovations, 12, 88–93
15. Makhmudova Muyassar, & Nargiza Karimova. (2023). THEORETICAL ASPECT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE OF INTERETHNIC COMMUNICATION AMONG STUDENTS. UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH, 1(7), 89–94.

16. Rasulova, Azizaxon Muydinovna, & Xusanova, Ma'Rifat Axmadjonovna (2022). POETIK NUTQDA SINONIMLARDAN FOYDALANISH MAHORATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10-2), 807-811.
17. Xusanova, M. R. A. (2021). THE USE OF ARCHAISM IN THE WORKS OF FARIDA AFROZ. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 252-254.
18. Xusanova Ma'rifat Axmadjonovna., Asomiddinova Gulruh Alijonovna. TIL ESTETIKASIGA DOIR. *Analytical Journal of Education and Development* Volume: 03 Issue: 03 | Mar-2023 ISSN: 2181-2624 www.sciencebox.uz 262-265.
19. Karimova Nargiza Mamatkadirovna. (2023). THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING STUDENTS FOR COMMUNICATION. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 16, 214–217.
20. Kamilova, U. M. I. D. A., Atakhodjaeva, G. U. L. C. H. E. K. H. R. A., Abdullaeva Ch, M. D., Zakirova, G., & Tagaeva, D. (2022). Features in the processes of left ventricular remodeling depending on the degree of renal dysfunction in patients with chronic heart failure. *Int J Biomed*, 12(2), 218-21.
21. Xusanova, M. R. A. (2016). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНО-СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИХ НЕОЛОГИЗМОВ-ПРИЗНАК СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКОГО СВОЕОБРАЗИЯ. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (5-1), 125-130.17.
22. Хидиров, Х. Н. (2018). Social justice and the process of education, and their mutual influence in the philosophical views of Abu Nasr al-Farabi. *Молодой ученый*, (14), 262-263